

CERTAIN ISSUES IN THE FIELD OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article discusses climate change issues in Uzbekistan, the country's legislative framework on this issue, and the steps taken to implement the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the “Uzbekistan-2030” Strategy. Uzbekistan was the first country in Central Asia to take significant steps to adapt the country to the consequences of climate change, accumulating its own funds and attracting international financial and technical assistance.*

Keywords: *UN, UNFCCC, Kyoto Protocol, Paris Agreement, climate change, greenhouse gas, “Uzbekistan-2030” strategy, Yashil Makon.*

Today, climate change is recognized by the global community as one of the most serious challenges facing humanity. Researchers have already demonstrated that climate change affects all areas of human activity and necessitates urgent measures to prevent negative consequences and adapt to new living conditions. Currently, scientific evidence increasingly shows that human economic activities significantly impact the climate, particularly due to greenhouse gas emissions resulting from the combustion of fossil fuels. Global climate change has become one of the most pressing issues of our time, affecting all countries around the world and posing a serious barrier to sustainable development. The observed increase in temperatures is leading to extreme natural phenomena worldwide, such as droughts, storms, wildfires, heavy rainfall, and floods.

Uzbekistan, along with other Central Asian countries, ranks among those most frequently encountering ecological crises. According to data from Uzgidromet, from 1880 to the present day, the average annual temperature in Uzbekistan has risen by approximately 1.6°C (from 13.2°C to 14.8°C), which is higher than the average rates observed globally. Experts predict that between 2030 and 2050, air temperatures in the region may increase by an additional 1.5 to 3°C.

Notably, Uzbekistan is considered one of the most vulnerable countries to climate change. According to expert assessments, further increases in greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere will heighten the risks of water and food shortages due to drought, increase the duration and intensity of the hot season leading to a rise in public health issues, and contribute to the recurrence of dangerous phenomena such as floods and landslides. Moreover, warming will exacerbate ecological problems in these regions. Calculations by World Bank experts indicate that by the end of the 21st century, if current trends continue, the average global temperature could rise by 4 degrees Celsius, while in Central Asia, this figure could reach 7 degrees Celsius. Over the last 50-60 years, the area of glaciers in the region has decreased by approximately 30% due to global climate change. By 2050, water resources in Syr Darya basin are expected to decrease by up to 5%, and in Amu Darya basin by up to 15%. The ongoing changes brought about by global climate change and the sensitivity of the country's natural resource complex underscore the necessity for a coherent climate policy.

Consequently, the United Nations Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), adopted on 9 May 1992, aims to stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere at a level that would prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system [1]. Uzbekistan

joined the IOC in 1993. In 1999, Uzbekistan ratified the Kyoto Protocol [5], an international agreement that obliges developed countries to reduce or stabilize greenhouse gas emissions. In December 2015, the Paris Agreement was adopted, replacing the UN Kyoto Protocol to strengthen a comprehensive response to the growing global risks associated with climate change. The Paris Agreement entered into force in 2020. Uzbekistan signed the Paris Agreement on 19 April 2017 and ratified it on 2 November 2018. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Ratification of the Paris Agreement" (No. 491) was adopted on October 2, 2018.

Furthermore, the goal of Paris Agreement is to accelerate the implementation of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change, to keep the increase in the global average temperature below 2 °C compared to the pre-industrial period (1750) and to limit the temperature increase to 1.5 °C, which aims to reduce global greenhouse gas emissions by 40-70% by 2050 and to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 2100. The goal is to achieve zero or negative gas emissions.

According to Article 4 of Paris Agreement, signatory and acceding parties are required to prepare and report to the relevant secretariat a nationally determined contribution to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions that the country wants to achieve by 2030. The nationally determined contribution is the main mechanism for making national efforts to promote the global goals of Paris Agreement. Uzbekistan's main commitment under Paris Agreement until 2021 was to reduce greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP by 10% by 2030. In 2021, Uzbekistan increased its quantitative commitments under Paris Agreement and by 2030 intends to reduce greenhouse gas emissions per unit of GDP by 35% instead of 10% from the 2010 level. [6]

Specifically, Uzbekistan includes measures and actions to mitigate and adapt for the period up to 2030. Activities to implement the estimated contribution determined at the national level are being implemented rapidly and make a significant contribution to the development of the economy of Uzbekistan. In addition, in accordance with Articles 4.1. and 12.1. The UN International Panel on Climate Change requires that countries that are members of the Convention periodically submit their national communications on climate change to the UN Committee on Climate Change - a report on the implementation of the Hadley Convention.

As a result, the national message describes in detail the actions and measures taken at the national level aimed at preventing climate change, adapting to it, developing and transferring technologies, providing education and raising awareness of various social strata.

In contrast, as a country party to Paris Agreement, Uzbekistan is implementing a policy aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and adapting to climate change in the main sectors of the economy.

Thus, the leadership and government of the country have adopted a number of documents related to the regulation of actions and implementation of measures in the field of climate change. In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PR-4477 dated 04.10.2019, the Strategy for the Transition to a Green Economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2030 has been developed by Uzhydromet together with the relevant ministries and departments. Also, an Interdepartmental Council has been formed to promote and implement this Strategy. In accordance with the Action Plan (Roadmap) of this Strategy, each ministry and department has been assigned tasks to mitigate or adapt to the effects of climate change [7].

Notably the UN and its partners in Uzbekistan are working to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals: 17 interrelated and ambitious goals aimed at addressing key development challenges facing people in Uzbekistan and around the world. Uzbekistan has reaffirmed its

commitment to an integrated approach to multilateral partnership to achieve the global agenda and sixteen national goals (SDGs) in the field of sustainable development by 2030.

In order to successfully implement the sustainable development goals, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the Decree on the Strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" [1]. The first article of this decree mentions the five main ideas of the Strategy, which note the importance of creating favorable environmental conditions for the population by 2030. To implement this idea, two main goals were developed. The first goal is devoted to water management reforms, and the second to environmental protection reforms.

Additionally, reforms in the water supply network include: improving the culture of rational use of water and efficiency of water consumption in the republic, ensuring rational use of water in the agricultural network, developing the irrigation system and water-saving technologies, the private sector in the management of the industry and the widespread introduction of public-private partnership mechanisms, reducing the energy consumption of pumping stations as part of the widespread introduction of "green energy" technologies.

Similarly, in the field of environmental protection, the following goals are envisaged: to radically improve the environmental situation in the republic, eliminate environmental problems affecting human life, expand the national project "Green Space" aimed at stabilizing the environmental situation.

Within the framework of this goal, it is planned to plant 200 million tree seedlings annually and increase the level of greening of the republic to 30%. The next goal is to expand the area of forests. This measure is necessary to protect land from erosion and reclaim objects from sand piles.

Thus, by adopting the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030", Uzbekistan shows the whole world that it is ready to implement the UN SDGs and is taking specific steps to implement them. It is worth noting that it is important to constantly monitor the implementation of goals, keep reports and analyze the tasks being performed. The Republic of Uzbekistan will continue to strive to develop and strengthen international cooperation in the fight against climate change. The country fulfills its international obligations, protecting its national interests and actively participating in the fight against climate change on a global scale.

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